

Consensus-Based Resource Allocation Strategy With Hormone-Based Workload Scheduler in Edge-Fog-Cloud Continuum

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Abstract—Balancing workloads across the edge–fog–cloud continuum remains a critical challenge, where distributed resources must collaborate under dynamic conditions. Inspired by principles of swarm intelligence, this paper develops a novel consensus-based resource allocation strategy with a hormone-based workload scheduler that enables edge agents to achieve local balance and collectively optimize global workload scheduling. We first propose a standard consensus protocol to manage the dynamic resource update and discuss the stability in the presence of disturbances. After that, a disturbance compensator is introduced into the consensus strategy to improve the robustness. The consensus-based resource allocation (CBRA) strategy is then combined with a hormone-based workload scheduler, forming an integrated solution for decentralized workload management. Using the COSMOS (Continuum Optimization for Swarm-based Multi-tier Orchestration System) simulation framework, we first verify the convergence of the resource update under the consensus algorithm. Then, we evaluate the performance of the integrated system under hormone-based workload scheduling with CBRA strategy. The results reveal that the workload management under the hormone-based workload scheduling with the CBRA strategy outperforms the baseline algorithms, such as HBA scheduling without CBRA, and other previous works because of the lower communication costs and dependency on higher layers. In general, the new approach is more adaptive to the initial resource distribution. Furthermore, the proposed integrated algorithm is also applied in the mobility use case. It not only reveals the scalability but also outperforms the baseline algorithms in large-scale mobility use case.

Index Terms—Consensus control, resource allocation, hormone-based algorithm, workload scheduler, edge-fog-cloud continuum.

I. INTRODUCTION

OVER the past decades, the studies on distributed computing paradigms, especially the edge–fog–cloud continuum, have attracted considerable interest with the increasing application of Internet of Things (IoT) devices. In contrast to centralized cloud computing, the edge-fog-cloud continuum enables localized decision-making and data processing by integrating the strengths of the edge, fog, and cloud computing paradigms [1]. However, managing such a workload scheduler more effectively

and adaptively remains a challenge due to resource and communication constraints [2].

In the edge-fog-cloud continuum, the goal of the workload management is to allocate computational tasks efficiently across the edge, fog, and cloud layers. The cloud centers can provide unlimited resources but suffer from latency, communication overhead, and security concerns [3]. The edge layer comprises resource-constrained devices but enables task processing locally and instantly, while the fog layer acts as an intermediate to bridge the gap between edge and cloud [4]. Inspired by natural collectives, swarm intelligence offers decentralized and self-organizing mechanisms that enable adaptive decision-making in dynamic and distributed environments [5]. Another issue that may affect the performance of the swarm intelligence algorithm is the uneven initial resource distribution across the edge network in the continuum. Proposing a workload management scheduler in the edge-fog-cloud continuum to minimize the communication cost and the dependency on the higher layers, while increasing the adaptability, is still an open balancing issue.

This work addresses the challenge of workload management in the edge–fog–cloud continuum by developing an integrated algorithmic approach. We first propose an innovative resource allocation strategy based on a consensus mechanism, introducing a standard consensus-based resource allocation (CBRA) protocol to balance edge-layer resources under disturbances and analyzing its stability. After that, we improve the CBRA strategy by introducing a compensator in the controller to tackle the unknown disturbances, and then present a continuous form of the protocol. The stability analysis is also provided via Lyapunov method [6]. Moreover, we integrate the CBRA strategy with the workload scheduler that uses the hormone-based algorithm (HBA), developing an integrated algorithm to handle the workload management. In the next stage, we implement the integrated algorithm to COSMOS (Continuum Optimization for Swarm-based Multi-tier Orchestration System) [7], a simulation framework for the edge-fog-cloud continuum. The convergence of the CBRA strategy is first validated for the resource update. Then we explore the performance of the integrated algorithm and compare it with some baseline algorithms, such as HBA scheduling without CBRA, and other previous works. It can be observed from the simulation results that the workload management with the integrated algorithm enables higher adaptivity as well as lower communication costs and dependency on fog and cloud layers, which is better than that using baseline algorithms.

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Moreover, we also implement the proposed integrated algorithm in the mobility use case. The integrated algorithm exhibits scalability and performs better than the baseline algorithm for the large-scale mobility use case. The main contributions can be summarized as follows.

- We propose a novel resource allocation strategy on the basis of a consensus approach. A standard CBRA strategy is presented for the edge resource agents to evenly allocate the resource pool. We also provide the stability analysis of the standard CBRA in the presence of unknown disturbances.
- We modify the standard CBRA, and then design a CBRA strategy with a compensator to deal with the unknown disturbances. The introduced compensation mechanism can improve the robustness of the strategy. Moreover, we improve the compensation function in a continuous form to avoid chattering. The stability of the CBRA with a compensator can be ensured by Lyapunov method. This CBRA strategy can not only achieve the balanced allocation but also guarantee robustness under unknown disturbances.
- We integrate the CBRA strategy into the workload scheduler with the HBA and apply the integrated algorithm to the edge-fog-cloud continuum in COSMOS framework. We compare the performance of the integrated algorithm with some baseline algorithms, such as HBA scheduling without CBRA, and other previous works. Simulation results show that the integrated algorithm outperforms the baseline algorithms because of the enhanced adaptability, while minimizing the communication costs and the dependency on the fog and cloud layers.
- We implement the proposed integrated algorithm in the mobility use case. The results reveal that the integrated algorithm exhibits scalability and outperforms the baseline algorithms for the large-scale mobility use case.

II. RELATED WORK

In this section, we review the previous work related to workload management, swarm intelligence, and consensus control.

Workload management refers to a discipline that integrates the monitoring and control of computational workflows, as well as the scheduling and allocation of resources to enhance system reliability and maximize performance [8]. The authors in [9] implemented a novel hierarchical game-theoretical framework to solve the task offloading problem in edge computing. Specifically, the optimization process was decoupled into a two-stage process of distributed channel access and resource pricing. In [10], a resource-aware task grouping and scheduling protocol was developed for edge computing systems to enhance the quality of service. The resource competition among tasks with deadline constraints was addressed by proposing a group-based scheduling strategy. In another work, the deep reinforcement learning approach was used in [11] to deal with time-varying workload scheduling for the cloud servers. The priority queues and parallel graph attention mechanisms were integrated to improve resource utilization efficiency and scheduling performance. However, in the works mentioned above, the computing paradigms were considered to be separated. The authors

in [12] proposed an online learning scheduler based on proximal policy optimization for workflow scheduling in the edge-cloud computing paradigm. A novel graph neural network and an intrinsic reward mechanism were designed for task embedding to address the lag effect in workload management. In another work, the availability of the edge-fog-cloud continuum was discussed in [13], where the edge, fog, and cloud computing layers were seamlessly connected. Moreover, the edge analytics of the edge-fog-cloud continuum was investigated in [14]. The approaches, including serverless data pipelines, distributed computing for collaborative analytics, and federated learning, were discussed in this paper. Nevertheless, it remains an open problem to manage the edge-fog-cloud continuum more effectively because the continuum involves highly diverse and widely distributed devices, and still requires integrated solutions for task offloading and resource allocation [15].

This brings us to swarm intelligence, a self-organizing technique that enables adaptive resource allocation strategies throughout the continuum [5]. The authors in [16] combined particle swarm optimization with value-based reinforcement learning to tackle the continuous control issues. In another work, particle swarm optimization was applied in [17] to schedule workflow in clouds. The proposed hybrid algorithm integrated particle swarm optimization with a heuristic method for task allocation to reduce the execution costs. The authors in [18] introduced a proximity-aware application management framework for the edge-cloud continuum. The ACO was implemented as decentralized clustering mechanism to organize the computing nodes into logical groups managed by dedicated orchestrators. In other work, ACO was implemented in [19] to solve the workload placement issue in the edge-fog-cloud continuum. The demand agents play the role of ants to release the pheromone on the resource agents to indicate the resource availability. The rule of the demand agents selecting the next resource agents is based on the pheromone values and communication costs. Furthermore, the authors in [20] applied the ACO for data management in the edge-fog-cloud continuum. This approach adopted pheromone-based path-finding for data relocation to reduce query latency and network traffic in distributed knowledge graphs. Another bio-inspired approach derived from swarm intelligence is the hormone-based algorithm (HBA) based on the artificial hormone system [21]. The HBA was implemented in [22] to address the lifetime issue of the sensor networks. This method allows nodes to make local decisions based on received hormonal signals to improve network longevity under energy constraints. A hormone-inspired system was established in [23] for robot swarms to adaptively allocate themselves to environments. In another work, the hormone algorithm was designed in [24] for the production scheduling problem. The machines and lots were modelled as autonomous agents that can exchange hormone signals. This decentralized and self-organizing strategy reduced production time and improved flow factor compared with conventional first-come-first-served approaches. After that, the agent-based modeling of the job-shop scheduling problem was presented in [25] including the hormone algorithm. The authors in [26] provided a workload scheduler with the HBA in the edge-fog-cloud continuum. Three processes

were considered in the hormone update rule. After that, the pods can choose the suitable resource agents based on hormone level and communication costs to decrease the dependency on the higher layers and communication costs. However, how to further improve the adaptivity of the HBA is still a challenge when designing the workload management, especially when the resource distribution across the edge layer is highly imbalanced.

Distributed consensus control is a fundamental approach in multi-agent systems that enables agents to reach agreement through local information [6]. The principles of consensus techniques can be extended and implemented in a wide range of domains, such as network management and optimization, deep reinforcement learning, robotic formation, etc. (see [27], [28], [29], [30], [31], [32]). The authors in [33] proposed a consensus-based training method for networked robotic manipulators. The consensus method was implemented for the critic and actor parameters in the neural network. In [34], a novel consensus mechanism was introduced to keep the fairness of the system in cloud computing. This mechanism incorporated a structured and cluster-based approach for miner selection to ensure decentralized governance and sustained fairness across participating service providers. Moreover, a decentralized optimization approach based on consensus was provided in [35] for edge computing. A stochastic approximation was integrated in the error-control coding strategies. The proposed approach enhanced robustness against link failures and straggler nodes while maintaining communication efficiency. In [36], the consensus method was combined with federated learning based on blockchain in IoT applications. The reinforcement learning and freshness-aware aggregation strategy were introduced in the algorithm to increase model convergence, system throughput, and load balancing across distributed nodes. Moreover, the authors in [37] proposed a fully decentralized resource selection mechanism based on a consensus-based bundle algorithm for self-organizing cloud-edge systems. The resource agents could allocate computational tasks collaboratively through iterative bidding and consensus phases to increase efficiency and scalability. To sum up, it can be obtained that the consensus mechanism can be selected as a candidate algorithm to improve the performance of workload management.

III. PRELIMINARIES AND PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we present some preliminaries related to agent-based modeling of the edge-fog-cloud continuum and concepts in graph theory. Then we describe the main objectives of this work.

A. System Model and Laplacian Matrix

1) *Resource Agent*: The resource agents stand for the networked resource pools across the edge-fog-cloud continuum. They offer CPU and memory (MEM) resources to serve the arriving demands. Specifically, the resource agents on the edge layer are basic IoT devices such as mobile robots, laptops, smartphones, and so on. For the fog and cloud layers, they are micro data centers and cloud servers. It is well-known that more

requests can be served on higher layers, but with privacy and latency issues.

Considering Q resource agents in the continuum. Suppose that there are Q_e , Q_f , and Q_c resource agents in the edge, fog, and cloud layers, respectively. We have $Q = Q_e + Q_c + Q_f$. Let $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{V}, \mathcal{E})$ be the undirected interaction topology of the edge-fog-cloud continuum. \mathcal{V} and $\mathcal{E} \subset \mathcal{V} \times \mathcal{V}$ are node and edge set. They represent the set of resource agents and their connections in the continuum. We denote $\mathcal{V}_e = \{v_1, \dots, v_{Q_e}\}$, $\mathcal{V}_f = \{v_{Q_e+1}, \dots, v_{Q_e+Q_f}\}$, and $\mathcal{V}_c = \{v_{Q_e+Q_f+1}, \dots, v_Q\}$ as the set of the resource agent in the edge, fog, and cloud paradigm. It follows that $\mathcal{V} = \mathcal{V}_e \cup \mathcal{V}_f \cup \mathcal{V}_c = \{v_1, \dots, v_Q\}$. $\forall v_i, v_j \in \mathcal{V}$, $(v_i, v_j) \in \mathcal{E}$ if the resource agents v_i and v_j are connected. Then, we can define the neighbor set of the agent v_i as

$$\mathcal{N}_i = \{v_j \in \mathcal{V} : (v_i, v_j) \in \mathcal{E}\} \quad (1)$$

Both inter- and intra-connections are considered in the edge-fog-cloud continuum. Let \mathcal{E}_{ee} and \mathcal{E}_{ff} be the set of inter-connections in edge and fog paradigms. For intra-connections. Define \mathcal{E}_{ef} and \mathcal{E}_{fc} as the connection set from edge to fog and from fog to cloud. There are no connections between each cloud server because they are independent. There is also no direct communication from edge devices to cloud providers since the fog paradigm acts as an intermediate layer in the continuum. Hence, we have $\mathcal{E} = \mathcal{E}_{ee} \cup \mathcal{E}_{ef} \cup \mathcal{E}_{fc} \cup \mathcal{E}_{ff}$.

The virtual hormone signal is introduced in the edge-fog-cloud continuum. We define a novel behavior, hormone releasing, on each resource agent. The hormone level can reflect the local available resources on each resource agent. In this way, the demand agent can determine and choose a suitable resource agent.

2) *Demand Agent*: The demand agents represent the incoming requests to the continuum. We consider them as ‘‘pods’’ in the Kubernetes [38] context with various requirements of CPU and memory resources. Define $\mu \in (0, 1]$ as the frequency of arriving pods. It reveals that the entry of demand agents into the continuum is determined by an exponential random variable μ . The demand agents can detect the hormone signals from the resource agents to decide which resource agent to be served. Then, the pods will evaluate the availability of the resources on the chosen resource agent. If both CPU and memory resources are enough, pods will be served here. Otherwise, the demand agents will move to a resource agent from the neighborhood based on the hormone level and communication costs, and they recheck the resource availability until they find an agent with enough CPU and memory units. The allocated resources will be released once the demand agents complete the execution.

3) *Laplacian Matrix*: In order to characterize the structure of a graph for further network analysis. We introduce the Laplacian matrix here. Considering the interaction topology $\mathcal{G}_e = (\mathcal{V}_e, \mathcal{E}_e)$ in the edge layer. Define the adjacency matrix of the graph \mathcal{G}_e as $\mathcal{A}_e = [a_{ij}] \in \mathbb{R}^{Q_e \times Q_e}$. The entry $a_{ij} > 0$ if $(v_i, v_j) \in \mathcal{E}_e$, $i \neq j$, otherwise $a_{ij} = 0$. Then, we can introduce the Laplacian matrix \mathcal{L}_e defined as $\mathcal{L}_e = \mathcal{D}_e - \mathcal{A}_e$, where $\mathcal{D}_e = \text{diag}\{d_{11}, \dots, d_{Q_e Q_e}\}$ with $d_{ii} = \sum_{j \neq i} a_{ij}$. Denote the eigenvalues of \mathcal{L}_e as $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{Q_e}$. It can be

observed that \mathcal{L}_e is non-negative definite and $\mathcal{L}_e \mathbf{1}_{Q_e} = 0$ with $\mathbf{1}_{Q_e} = [1, \dots, 1]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{Q_e}$ [39]. Hence, we can suppose that $0 = \lambda_1 \leq \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_{Q_e}$.

B. Main Objectives

The resource update on each edge resource agent can be described as

$$r_i(t+1) = r_i(t) + T * (d_i(t) + u_i(t)), \quad i \in \{1, \dots, Q_E\} \quad (2)$$

where $r_i = [r_i^{CPU}, r_i^{MEM}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^2$ is the resource pool that includes CPU and memory for the i^{th} resource agent. $d_i(t)$ denotes the disturbance introduced which is unknown. It refers to the uncertainties in the environment during the update process. $u_i(t)$ is the control input for the resource agent v_i and $T \in (0, 1]$ is the time interval. Denote $r = [r_1^T, \dots, r_{Q_E}^T]^T$, $d = [d_1^T, \dots, d_{Q_E}^T]^T$, and $u = [u_1^T, \dots, u_{Q_E}^T]^T$. The compact form of (2) can be expressed as

$$r(t+1) = r(t) + T * (d(t) + u(t)) \quad (3)$$

We should provide the following assumptions

Assumption 1: The introduced disturbance $d_i(t)$ is bounded. In other words, $\|d_i(t)\| \leq d^*$, $d^* \in \mathbb{R}^+$.

According to Assumption 1 and the average inequality, we can get $\|d\| \leq \sqrt{Q_e} d^*$.

Assumption 2: There exists at least one spanning tree in the network of the edge resource agent.

Assumption 2 reveals that the edge resource network is connected, which is commonly used in distributed cooperative control [6]. Then we can obtain that $\lambda_1 = 0$ is the only zero eigenvalue of the Laplacian matrix \mathcal{L}_e . Hence, for the other eigenvalues, we have $0 < \lambda_2 \leq \dots \leq \lambda_{Q_e}$.

The problem formulation of this paper is presented in the following precise form. Suppose that the resource update process of each edge resource agent can be described as (2). The main objectives of this work can be summarized as: 1) How to design a resource allocation strategy motivated by the consensus method. 2) How to enhance the robustness of the CBRA strategy against unknown disturbances. 3) How to modify the CBRA strategy in a continuous form. 4) How to integrate the CBRA strategy into a hormone-based scheduling algorithm to improve workload management performance.

Remark 1: System robustness is an important part to guarantee the security of the framework. It reflects the capability of the system to counter the uncertainties in the environment and preserve stable behavior. This tolerance to unknown disturbances inherently enhances the security of the system. Hence, the disturbances are introduced in the resource update process that can be regarded as a simplified form of constrained adversarial influence [40], [41], which forms the foundation for the subsequent theoretical analysis.

IV. METHODOLOGY

In this section, we first present a resource allocation protocol based on the standard consensus approach and discuss the stability of the algorithm. After that, a compensator is introduced in

Fig. 1. Sketch of the consensus algorithm for resource allocation in three agents.

the controller to tackle the unknown disturbances. We further modify the compensator as a continuous form. Finally, we provide a workload scheduler based on swarm intelligence and integrate the CBRA strategy with the HBA scheduling.

A. Resource Allocation Strategy on Resource Agents

1) *Standard Consensus Protocol:* We first pay attention to applying the traditional consensus controller in the resource system (2), which is designed as

$$u_i(t) = \kappa \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} a_{ij} (r_j(t) - r_i(t)) \quad (4)$$

where κ represents the consensus gain, which will be designed later. An example of the consensus algorithm is demonstrated in Fig. 1 for resource allocation in three agents.

Let $\bar{r}_i(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{Q_e} r_i(t) / Q_e$ be the average resource for each resource agent. Define the consensus error $\xi_i(t) = r_i(t) - \bar{r}_i(t)$ and $\xi(t) = [\xi_1(t), \dots, \xi_{Q_e}(t)]^T$. We can present the following theorem.

Theorem 1: Suppose that Assumptions 1 and 2 hold. Applying the consensus protocol (4) to the resource update process (2). Given a constant $\gamma \in (0, 1)$, if the consensus gain κ is selected as

$$\kappa = \frac{\gamma}{\lambda_{Q_e}} \quad (5)$$

The consensus error will converge to a bounded set

$$\Gamma = \left\{ \xi : \|\xi\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2Q_e(2 + T\lambda_{\min})}{\lambda_{\min}^2}} d^* \right\} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\lambda_{\min} = 2\gamma \frac{\lambda_2}{\lambda_{Q_e}} - \gamma^2 \frac{\lambda_2^2}{\lambda_{Q_e}^2} \quad (7)$$

Proof: Substituting (4) in (2), $\forall i \in \{1, \dots, Q_E\}$ we have

$$r_i(t+1) = r_i(t) + \kappa T \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} a_{ij} (r_j(t) - r_i(t)) + T d_i(t) \quad (8)$$

From the definition of the Laplacian matrix, we can write the compact form of (8) as

$$r(t+1) = (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2) r(t) + T d(t) \quad (9)$$

where I_{2Q_e} (I_2) is the identity matrix with dimension $2Q_e$ (2) and \otimes is the Kronecker product.

Let the orthogonal matrix $\Omega = [\Omega_1, \Omega_2, \dots, \Omega_{Q_e}] \in \mathbb{R}^{Q_e \times Q_e}$ be the eigenmatrix of \mathcal{L}_e , where $\Omega_i \in \mathbb{R}^{Q_e}$ stand for the eigenvectors of $\lambda_i, \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, Q_e\}$. It is obvious that $\Omega_1 = \frac{\mathbf{1}_{Q_e}}{\sqrt{Q_e}}$ and

$$\Lambda = \Omega^T \mathcal{L}_e \Omega \quad (10)$$

where $\Lambda = \text{diag}\{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{Q_e}\}$.

Define the state $\delta(t)$ as

$$\delta(t) = (\Omega^T \otimes I_2)r(t) = [\delta_0^T(t), \bar{\delta}^T(t)]^T \quad (11)$$

with $\delta_0(t) = (\frac{\mathbf{1}_{Q_e}^T}{\sqrt{Q_e}} \otimes I_2)r(t)$, $\bar{\delta}(t) = [\bar{\delta}_1^T(t), \dots, \bar{\delta}_{Q_e-1}^T(t)]^T$, and $\bar{\delta}_i(t) = (\Omega_{i+1}^T \otimes I_2)r(t), \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, Q_e - 1\}$. Then, we can obtain that

$$\begin{aligned} r(t) &= (\Omega \otimes I_2)\delta(t) \\ &= \frac{\mathbf{1}_{Q_e}}{\sqrt{Q_e}} \otimes \delta_0(t) + \sum_{i=1}^{Q_e-1} \Omega_{i+1}(t) \otimes \bar{\delta}_i(t) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Combining (9), (10), (11), and (12) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(t+1) &= (\Omega^T \otimes I_2)((I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)r(t) + Td(t)) \\ &= (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \Lambda \otimes I_2)\delta(t) + (\Omega^T \otimes I_2)Td(t) \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Based on the definition of $\delta(t)$ in (11), it can be obtained that

$$\bar{\delta}(t+1) = (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \bar{\Lambda} \otimes I_2)\bar{\delta}(t) + (\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)Td(t) \quad (14)$$

where $\bar{\Lambda} = \text{diag}\{\lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_{Q_e}\} > 0$ and $\bar{\Omega} = [\Omega_2, \dots, \Omega_{Q_e}]$.

Denote $\bar{r} = [\bar{r}_1, \dots, \bar{r}_{Q_e}]^T$. Based on the definition of average resource, we can get

$$\xi(t) = r(t) - \bar{r}(t) = (I_{2Q_e} - \frac{1}{Q_e}(\mathbf{1}_{Q_e} \otimes I_2)(\mathbf{1}_{Q_e}^T \otimes I_2))r(t) \quad (15)$$

From (11), (15), and the properties of the eigenvectors, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(t) &= (I_{2Q_e} - (\Omega_1 \Omega_1^T \otimes I_2))r(t) \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^{Q_e-1} \Omega_{i+1}(t) \otimes \bar{\delta}_i(t) = (\bar{\Omega} \otimes I_2)\bar{\delta}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

It can be obtained that $\|\xi(t)\| = \|\bar{\delta}(t)\|$ and $\|\bar{\Omega} \otimes I_2\| = 1$.

We choose the Lyapunov candidate $V(t)$ as

$$V(t) = \frac{1}{2T} \xi^T(t) \xi(t) \quad (17)$$

Let $\Delta V = V(t+1) - V(t)$. It can be calculated that

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V &= \frac{1}{2T} \bar{\delta}^T(t+1)\bar{\delta}(t+1) - \frac{1}{2T} \bar{\delta}^T(t)\bar{\delta}(t) \\ &\leq -\frac{1}{2} \bar{\delta}^T(t)((2\kappa \bar{\Lambda} - \kappa^2 T \bar{\Lambda}^2) \otimes I_2)\bar{\delta}(t) + \frac{1}{2} T d^T(t)d(t) \\ &\quad + \bar{\delta}^T(t)(I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \bar{\Lambda} \otimes I_2)(\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)d(t) \\ &\leq -\frac{1}{2} \bar{\delta}^T(t)((2\kappa \bar{\Lambda} - \kappa^2 \bar{\Lambda}^2) \otimes I_2)\bar{\delta}(t) + \frac{1}{2} T d^T(t)d(t) \\ &\quad + \bar{\delta}^T(t)(I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \bar{\Lambda} \otimes I_2)(\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)d(t) \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

It can be observed from (5) that the eigenvalues of $2\kappa \bar{\Lambda} - \kappa^2 \bar{\Lambda}^2$ can be expressed as

$$2\gamma \frac{\lambda_i}{\lambda_{Q_e}} - \gamma^2 \frac{\lambda_i^2}{\lambda_{Q_e}^2}, \quad i \in \{2, \dots, Q_e\} \quad (19)$$

It is obvious that all the eigenvalues are positive from the selection of κ and the minimum eigenvalue λ_{\min} is defined in (7). Thus, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V &\leq -\frac{\lambda_{\min}}{2} \|\bar{\delta}(t)\|^2 + \sqrt{Q_e} \|\bar{\delta}(t)\| d^* + \frac{Q_e T}{2} d^{*2} \\ &\leq -\frac{\lambda_{\min}}{2} \|\xi(t)\|^2 + \sqrt{Q_e} \|\xi(t)\| d^* + \frac{Q_e T}{2} d^{*2} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

From the average inequality, we have

$$\sqrt{Q_e} \|\xi(t)\| d^* \leq \frac{\lambda_{\min}}{4} \|\xi(t)\|^2 + \frac{1}{\lambda_{\min}} Q_e d^{*2} \quad (21)$$

Combining (20) and (21), it can be obtained that

$$\Delta V = -\frac{\lambda_{\min}}{4} \|\xi(t)\|^2 + \left(\frac{1}{\lambda_{\min}} + \frac{T}{2}\right) Q_e d^{*2} \quad (22)$$

Define a bounded set as

$$\Gamma = \left\{ \xi : \|\xi\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2Q_e(2 + T\lambda_{\min})}{\lambda_{\min}^2} d^{*2}} \right\} \quad (23)$$

Let $\bar{\Gamma}$ be the supplementary set of Γ . If $\xi \in \Gamma$, we can conclude that $\Delta V \leq 0$. That is to say, the consensus error ξ converges to the bounded set Γ using the consensus protocol (4). This completes the proof. \square

Corollary 1: Suppose that Assumptions 1 and 2 hold. Applying the consensus protocol (4) to the resource update process (2). By introducing the same disturbance to each agent, the consensus error will converge to zero if

$$-I_{2Q_e} + M^2 \leq 0 \quad (24)$$

where $M = I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2$.

Proof: Since the graph is undirected, it can be obtained that $\mathcal{L}_e \mathbf{1}_{Q_e} = \mathbf{1}_{Q_e}^T \mathcal{L}_e = 0$. Let

$$\bar{P} = \frac{1}{Q_e} (\mathbf{1}_{Q_e} \otimes I_2)(\mathbf{1}_{Q_e}^T \otimes I_2) \quad (25)$$

It follows that

$$(\mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)\bar{P} = \bar{P}(\mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2) = 0 \quad (26)$$

Let $\tilde{d}(t) = (I_{2Q_e} - \bar{P})d(t)$. From (26), (15), and (9), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \xi(t+1) &= (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)(I_{2Q_e} - \bar{P})r(t) + \tilde{d}(t) \\ &= M\xi(t) + \tilde{d}(t) \end{aligned} \quad (27)$$

Since the introduced disturbance is the same for each resource agent, we have $d_1(t) = d_2(t) = \dots = d_{Q_e}(t)$. Then, it can be obtained that

$$\tilde{d}(t) = (I_{2Q_e} - \bar{P})d(t) = 0. \quad (28)$$

Substituting (28) into (27), the error system can be written as

$$\xi(t+1) = M\xi(t) \quad (29)$$

Selecting the Lyapunov function defined in (17), from (18) and (24) we can obtain that

$$\Delta V \leq -\frac{1}{2}\xi^T(t)(I_{2Q_e} - M^2)\xi(t) \leq 0 \quad (30)$$

That is to say, the consensus error converges to zero. This completes the proof. \square

2) *Consensus Protocol With Disturbance Compensator*: It can be observed that the consensus error will converge to a bounded set using the standard consensus protocol. Hence, we will develop a compensator to deal with the disturbance during the update process. Let

$$\mathcal{C}_i(t) = \sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_i} a_{ij}(r_j(t) - r_i(t)) \quad (31)$$

The consensus protocol with disturbance-compensator can be designed as

$$u_i(t) = \kappa \mathcal{C}_i(t) + D\mathcal{F}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t)) \quad (32)$$

where $\mathcal{F}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t))$ is the compensation function which is described as

$$\mathcal{F}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t)) = \begin{cases} \frac{\mathcal{C}_i(t)}{\|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\|}, & \text{when } \|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\| \neq 0 \\ 0, & \text{when } \|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\| = 0. \end{cases} \quad (33)$$

κ and D are control gains which will be designed later.

Denote $\mathcal{C}(t) = [\mathcal{C}_1^T(t), \dots, \mathcal{C}_{Q_e}^T(t)]^T$ and $\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t)) = [\mathcal{F}_1^T(\mathcal{C}_1(t)), \dots, \mathcal{F}_{Q_e}^T(\mathcal{C}_{Q_e}(t))]^T$. We have the following theorem

Theorem 2: Suppose that Assumptions 1 and 2 hold. Applying the consensus protocol (32) to the resource update process (2). If the control gain κ is chosen as (5), and D is selected as

$$D \geq \sqrt{Q_e}d^* \quad (34)$$

The consensus error will converge to a bounded set

$$\Gamma_1 = \left\{ \xi : \|\xi\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2T\Theta(\lambda_{Q_e}\bar{\lambda}_{\min} + 2\gamma^2\lambda_{Q_e}^2T)}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}^2}} \right\} \quad (35)$$

where $\Theta = Q_e(1 + \sqrt{Q_e})^2d^{*2}$ and

$$\bar{\lambda}_{\min} = 2\gamma\frac{\lambda_2^2}{\lambda_{Q_e}} - \gamma^2\frac{\lambda_2^3}{\lambda_{Q_e}^2} \quad (36)$$

Proof: Substituting (32) in (2), $\forall i \in \{1 \dots, Q_e\}$ we have

$$r_i(t+1) = r_i(t) + \kappa T\mathcal{C}_i(t) + DT\mathcal{F}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t)) + Td_i(t) \quad (37)$$

Based on the definition of the Laplacian matrix, it can be obtained from (15) and (26) that

$$-C(t) = (\mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)r(t) = (\mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)\xi(t) \quad (38)$$

Hence, the compact form of (37) can be expressed as

$$r(t+1) = (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T\mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)r(t) - DT\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t)) + Td(t) \quad (39)$$

Then from (11), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} \delta(t+1) &= (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T\Lambda \otimes I_2)\delta(t) + T(\Omega^T \otimes I_2)(d(t) \\ &\quad + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\delta}(t+1) &= (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T\bar{\Lambda} \otimes I_2)\bar{\delta}(t) + T(\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)(d(t) \\ &\quad + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

Choosing the Lyapunov function defined as

$$V = \frac{1}{2T}\xi^T(t)(\mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2)\xi(t) \quad (42)$$

Similar to (18), we can get

$$\Delta V \leq -\frac{1}{2}\bar{\delta}^T(t)((2\kappa\bar{\Lambda}^2 - \kappa^2\bar{\Lambda}^3) \otimes I_2)\bar{\delta}(t) + \Pi_1 + \Pi_2 \quad (43)$$

where

$$\Pi_1 = \bar{\delta}^T(t)((\bar{\Lambda} - \kappa T\bar{\Lambda}^2) \otimes I_2)(\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)(d(t) + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \quad (44)$$

and

$$\Pi_2 = \frac{T}{2}(d(t) + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t)))^T(\bar{\Lambda} \otimes I_2)(d(t) + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \quad (45)$$

According to the definition of the compensation function, we have $\|\mathcal{F}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t))\| \leq 1$. Then it can be obtained that

$$\|\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))\| = \sum_{i=1}^{Q_e} \sqrt{\|\mathcal{F}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t))\|^2} \leq \sqrt{Q_e} \quad (46)$$

Hence, on one hand, from (34), (45), and (47), we can get

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_2 &\leq \frac{T\lambda_{Q_e}}{2}(\|d(t)\| + D\|\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))\|)^2 \\ &\leq \frac{T\lambda_{Q_e}}{2}Q_e(1 + \sqrt{Q_e})^2d^{*2} = \frac{T\lambda_{Q_e}}{2}\Theta \end{aligned} \quad (47)$$

On the other hand, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_1 &= \bar{\delta}^T(t)(\bar{\Lambda}\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)(d(t) + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) + \Pi_3 \\ &= -C^T(t)(d(t) + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) + \Pi_3 \end{aligned} \quad (48)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_3 &= -\kappa T\xi(t)(\bar{\Omega}\bar{\Lambda}^2\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2)(d(t) + D\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \\ &\leq \gamma\lambda_{Q_e}T\|\xi(t)\|(\|d(t)\| + D\|\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t))\|) \\ &\leq \gamma\lambda_{Q_e}T\|\xi(t)\|(\sqrt{Q_e} + Q_e)d^* \\ &\leq \frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}{4}\|\xi(t)\|^2 + \frac{\gamma^2\lambda_{Q_e}^2T^2}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}\Theta \end{aligned} \quad (49)$$

Based on (34) and (38), together with the design of \mathcal{F} in (33), it can be implied that

$$\begin{aligned} -DC^T(t)\mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t)) &= -D\sum_{i=1}^{Q_e} \frac{\mathcal{C}_i^T(t)\mathcal{C}_i(t)}{\|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\|} = -D\sum_{i=1}^{Q_e} \|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\| \\ &\leq -D\|\mathcal{C}(t)\| = -\sqrt{Q_e}d^*\|\mathcal{C}(t)\| \end{aligned} \quad (50)$$

Combining with (48), we have

$$\Pi_1 \leq -C^T(t)d(t) - \sqrt{Q_e}d^*\|\mathcal{C}(t)\| + \Pi_3 \leq \Pi_3 \quad (51)$$

Substituting (47), (49), and (51) into (43)

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V &\leq -\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}{2} \|\bar{\delta}(t)\|^2 + \Pi_2 + \Pi_3 \\ &\leq -\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}{4} \|\xi(t)\|^2 + T\Theta \left(\frac{\lambda_{Q_e} \bar{\lambda}_{\min} + 2\gamma^2 \lambda_{Q_e}^2 T}{2\bar{\lambda}_{\min}} \right) \end{aligned} \quad (52)$$

Define a bounded set Γ_1 as

$$\Gamma_1 = \left\{ \xi : \|\xi\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2T\Theta(\lambda_{Q_e} \bar{\lambda}_{\min} + 2\gamma^2 \lambda_{Q_e}^2 T)}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}^2}} \right\} \quad (53)$$

Let $\bar{\Gamma}_1$ be the supplementary set of Γ_1 . If $\xi \in \bar{\Gamma}_1$, we can conclude that $\Delta V \leq 0$. That is to say, the consensus error ξ converges to the bounded set Γ_1 using the consensus protocol (32). This completes the proof. \square

Remark 2: The boundary of $\|\xi\|$ using the consensus protocol with a disturbance compensator is equivalent to $o(T^{1/2})$. In other words, the consensus error can be guaranteed in a small region if the time interval T is small enough. The resource update process (2) will change to continuous when $T \rightarrow 0$, and then $\|\xi\|$ can converge to zero with a disturbance compensator for continuous resource update. In contrast, the consensus error using the standard consensus protocol cannot be ensured such that $\|\xi(t)\| \rightarrow 0$ if $T \rightarrow 0$. Hence, the disturbance compensator plays a key role in maintaining the robustness of the resource update using the consensus method.

The disturbance compensator designed in (33) is not continuous. This discontinuous protocol is more sensitive to consensus errors and may trigger chattering during the update process. Hence, in the next stage, we focus on improving the compensation function in a continuous form to mitigate chattering and ensure a smoother and more stable resource update process. The modified consensus protocol with a continuous disturbance compensator is presented as

$$u_i(t) = \kappa \mathcal{C}_i(t) + D \bar{\mathcal{F}}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t)) \quad (54)$$

where $\bar{\mathcal{F}}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t))$ is a continuous compensation function which is provided as

$$\bar{\mathcal{F}}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t)) = \frac{2\mathcal{C}_i(t)}{\|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\| + \varepsilon} \quad (55)$$

with a threshold $\varepsilon > 0$. Let $\bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t)) = [\bar{\mathcal{F}}_1^T(\mathcal{C}_1(t)), \dots, \bar{\mathcal{F}}_{Q_e}^T(\mathcal{C}_{Q_e}(t))]^T$. The following theorem reveals the analysis of the robustness.

Theorem 3: Suppose that Assumptions 1 and 2 hold. Applying the continuous consensus protocol (54) to the resource update process (2). If the control gain κ is chosen as (5), and D is selected as (34). The consensus error will converge to a bounded set

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma_2 &= \left\{ \xi : \|\xi\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2T\Theta(\lambda_{Q_e} \bar{\lambda}_{\min} + 2\gamma^2 \lambda_{Q_e}^2 T)}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}^2} + \frac{4\sqrt{Q_e} d^* \varepsilon}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}} \right\} \\ &\quad (56) \end{aligned}$$

where $\bar{\Theta} = Q_e(1 + 2\sqrt{Q_e})^2 d^{*2}$.

Proof: The compact form of (2) using the continuous controller (54) can be written as

$$r(t+1) = (I_{2Q_e} - \kappa T \mathcal{L}_e \otimes I_2) r(t) + DT \bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t)) + Td(t) \quad (57)$$

Define the Lyapunov function shown in (42). Similar to (43), we have

$$\Delta V \leq -\frac{1}{2} \bar{\delta}^T(t) ((2\kappa \bar{\Lambda}^2 - \kappa^2 \bar{\Lambda}^3) \otimes I_2) \bar{\delta}(t) + \bar{\Pi}_1 + \bar{\Pi}_2 \quad (58)$$

with

$$\bar{\Pi}_1 = \bar{\delta}^T(t) ((\bar{\Lambda} - \kappa T \bar{\Lambda}^2) \otimes I_2) (\bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2) (d(t) + D \bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \quad (59)$$

and

$$\bar{\Pi}_2 = \frac{T}{2} (d(t) + D \bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t)))^T (\bar{\Lambda} \otimes I_2) (d(t) + D \bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \quad (60)$$

On one hand, since $\|\bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t))\| \leq 2$. It can be found from (47) that

$$\Pi_2 \leq \frac{T \lambda_{Q_e} \bar{\Theta}}{2} \quad (61)$$

On the other hand, we have

$$\bar{\Pi}_1 = -\mathcal{C}^T(t) (d(t) + D \bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t))) + \bar{\Pi}_3 \quad (62)$$

with

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi_3 &= -\kappa T \xi(t) (\bar{\Omega} \bar{\Lambda}^2 \bar{\Omega}^T \otimes I_2) (d(t) + D \bar{\mathcal{F}}(\mathcal{C}(t))) \\ &\leq \frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}{4} \|\xi(t)\|^2 + \frac{\gamma^2 \lambda_{Q_e}^2 T^2}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}} \bar{\Theta} \end{aligned} \quad (63)$$

If $\|\mathcal{C}(t)\| > \varepsilon$, we can get

$$\begin{aligned} -D \mathcal{C}^T(t) \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t)) &\leq -D \sum_{i=1}^{Q_e} \frac{2\mathcal{C}_i^T(t) \mathcal{C}_i(t)}{\|\mathcal{C}_i(t)\| + \|\mathcal{C}(t)\|} \\ &\leq -D \|\mathcal{C}(t)\| = -\sqrt{Q_e} d^* \|\mathcal{C}(t)\| \end{aligned} \quad (64)$$

Hence, according (51), we have

$$\bar{\Pi}_1 \leq \bar{\Pi}_3 \quad (65)$$

If $\|\mathcal{C}(t)\| \leq \varepsilon$, we have

$$-D \mathcal{C}^T(t) \mathcal{F}(\mathcal{C}(t)) \leq 0 \quad (66)$$

Then we can obtain that

$$\bar{\Pi}_1 \leq \bar{\Pi}_3 + \sqrt{Q_e} d^* \varepsilon \quad (67)$$

In other words, (67) always holds for both cases of $\|\mathcal{C}(t)\|$. Substituting (61), (63), and (67) into (58), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V &\leq -\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}{2} \|\bar{\delta}(t)\|^2 + \bar{\Pi}_2 + \bar{\Pi}_3 + \sqrt{Q_e} d^* \varepsilon \\ &\leq -\frac{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}{4} \|\xi(t)\|^2 + T\Theta \left(\frac{\lambda_{Q_e} \bar{\lambda}_{\min} + 2\gamma^2 \lambda_{Q_e}^2 T}{2\bar{\lambda}_{\min}} \right) \\ &\quad + \sqrt{Q_e} d^* \varepsilon \end{aligned} \quad (68)$$

Algorithm 1: CBRA Strategy.

Input: Interaction topology and disturbances
Output: Consensus value of the resources

- 1 Initialization;
- 2 **for** Each edge resource agent i **do**
- 3 **if** Agent $j \in \mathcal{N}_i$ **then**
- 4 $a_{ij} = 1$
- 5 **else**
- 6 $a_{ij} = 0$
- 7 Compute the consensus error $\mathcal{C}_i(t)$;
- 8 Select the parameters based on Theorem 3;
- 9 Obtain the compensator $\bar{\mathcal{F}}_i(\mathcal{C}_i(t))$ in (55);
- 10 Apply the consensus protocol (54);

Define a bounded set Γ_2 as

$$\Gamma_2 = \left\{ \xi : \|\xi\| \leq \sqrt{\frac{2T\Theta(\lambda_{Q_e}\bar{\lambda}_{\min} + 2\gamma^2\lambda_{Q_e}^2T)}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}^2} + \frac{4\sqrt{Q_e}d^*\varepsilon}{\bar{\lambda}_{\min}}} \right\} \quad (69)$$

Let $\bar{\Gamma}_2$ be the supplementary set of Γ_2 . If $\xi \in \bar{\Gamma}_2$, it can be obtained that $\Delta V \leq 0$. That is to say, the consensus error ξ converges to the bounded set Γ_2 using the continuous consensus protocol (54). This completes the proof. \square

The proposed CBRA strategy is illustrated in Algorithm 1.

B. Hormone-Based Workload Scheduler

In this section, we introduce a hormone-based workload scheduler proposed in [26]. The production of artificial hormones is defined as a special behavior in each resource agent related to the available resources. This hormone information can be detected by the pods. Then they will decide where to proceed next when necessary.

The update of the hormone level includes the hormone generation, diffusion, and evaporation. The generated hormone level $\Delta\mathcal{H}_g^i$ on the i^{th} resource agent is described as

$$\Delta\mathcal{H}_g^i = k_g \left(\frac{\mathcal{AR}_i^{CPU}}{r_i^{CPU}} + \frac{\mathcal{AR}_i^{MEM}}{r_i^{MEM}} \right) \quad (70)$$

where \mathcal{AR}_i^{CPU} and \mathcal{AR}_i^{MEM} stand for the available CPU and memory resources on the i^{th} resource agent, k_g is the release parameter. It can be observed from (70) that the hormone value released depends on the utilization of the resources in the agent during the generation process.

The diffusion process is also considered for the hormone update rule. The diffused hormone level in the i^{th} resource agent can be expressed as

$$\Delta\mathcal{H}_{d-}^i = k_d\Delta\mathcal{H}_g^i \quad (71)$$

where k_d represents the diffusion coefficient. The diffused hormone $\Delta\mathcal{H}_{d-}^i$ will be assigned to the neighbors of the resource agent i according to the communication cost. Each resource

agent can also obtain the diffused hormone from their neighbors. Denote the received hormone level on resource agent i as $\Delta\mathcal{H}_{d+}^i$. It can be written as

$$\Delta\mathcal{H}_{d+}^i = \sum_{v_l \in \mathcal{N}_i} \frac{\chi_{li}}{\sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \chi_{jl}} \Delta\mathcal{H}_d^l \quad (72)$$

where χ_{jl} is the inverse of the communication cost between the j^{th} and l^{th} resource agents.

The hormone value evaporates with a rate k_ρ at each iteration. Hence, the evaporation process of the hormone is expressed as

$$\mathcal{H}_i = (1 - k_\rho)\mathcal{H}_i \quad (73)$$

Combining (70), (71), (72), and (73), the hormone update rule with hormone generation, diffusion, and evaporation on the i^{th} resource agent can be concluded as

$$\mathcal{H}_i = (1 - k_\rho)\mathcal{H}_i + \Delta\mathcal{H}_g^i + \Delta\mathcal{H}_{d+}^i - \Delta\mathcal{H}_{d-}^i \quad (74)$$

The pods can obtain hormone information from each resource agent when they arrive in the continuum. They will start from the edge layer and select the first edge resource agent v_i with the following probability

$$\mathcal{P}_s^i = \frac{\mathcal{H}_i}{\sum_{k \in \mathcal{V}_e} \mathcal{H}_k} \quad (75)$$

Pods will be served here if the available resources in v_i are enough. Otherwise, they will choose another resource agent v_j from the neighbors of v_i (\mathcal{N}_i) with the probability designed as

$$\mathcal{P}_j = \frac{\chi_{ij}^{\alpha_c} \mathcal{H}_j^{\alpha_H}}{\sum_{v_j \in \mathcal{N}_i} \chi_{ij}^{\alpha_c} \mathcal{H}_j^{\alpha_H}} \quad (76)$$

where α_c and α_H denote the weighting parameters of communication costs and hormone value. The pods will then recheck the availability of resources until there are sufficient resources to serve them.

C. Integration and Discussion

To enhance workload management in the continuum, we integrate the CBRA strategy with the HBA workload scheduler. This combination brings bio-inspired scheduling together with a balanced resource distribution across the network. As a result, the continuum can avoid overloading and operate more smoothly. More demand agents can be executed locally with less communication costs.

Define the average consensus error as $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$. The CBRA strategy is implemented in the edge layer until $\|\bar{\mathcal{C}}\|$ is smaller than the threshold $\bar{\varepsilon}$. Each resource agent can exchange their current local resource states $r_i(t)$ with its neighbors. Then they compute the control input using the resource states $r_j(t)$ received from its neighboring agents based on the CBRA strategy. The resource allocation becomes more evenly distributed with each iteration. On the other hand, the task assignment of demand agents is managed through an HBA workload scheduler. Each pod can be attracted by the virtual hormone value. After that, they will make a decision based on the hormone level and communication costs to seek the most suitable resource agent. Combining with the CBRA strategy, the HBA workload scheduler can be operated in a balanced network to avoid the situation where some

Fig. 2. Architecture of the integrated algorithm that includes the HBA scheduling with CBRA strategy for the edge-fog-cloud continuum.

resource agents are overloaded while others are underutilized. Algorithm 2 demonstrates the integrator algorithm including the CBRA strategy and HBA workload scheduler. The architecture of the integrated algorithm is displayed in Fig. 2 for the edge-fog-cloud continuum, which includes the control loop of the CBRA strategy and examples of the possible paths for three incoming pods using HBA scheduling.

Remark 3: The node churn is one of the key issues that occurs in practical frameworks. On one hand, the integrated algorithm remains valid even in the presence of node churn, as long as the edge network without the leaving node continues to preserve at least one spanning tree. In this case, the framework can tolerate node churn if Assumption 2 still holds. On the other hand, we acknowledge that the robustness of the framework may be affected if Assumption 2 is broken in the presence of node churn. To address this issue, the resilient and switching-topology control strategies [42], [43] can be implemented in this framework to further improve the robustness of the edge-fog-cloud continuum.

Remark 4: The performance of the framework may be affected by some blockchain-level parameters. For instance, longer block intervals or higher consensus latency may prolong the time required to process state information and hinder the convergence of resource updates. Moreover, higher transaction costs may also reduce the frequency of on-chain updates, which may further affect the timeliness of resource allocation decisions. To mitigate these effects, techniques such as event-trigger mechanism [44] and off-chain methods [45], [46] are possible to be employed in this framework, helping the edge-fog-cloud continuum to maintain robustness and responsiveness in practical deployments.

We propose several metrics as key performance indicators (KPI) to evaluate the performance of the HBA workload scheduler with and without the CBRA strategy. If there are \mathcal{M} demand agents served in the continuum, with \mathcal{M}_{fog} and \mathcal{M}_{cloud} pods visiting fog and cloud layers. Let \mathcal{D}_f and \mathcal{D}_c be the dependency on the fog and cloud layers (DF and DC). They can be expressed as

$$\mathcal{D}_f = \frac{\mathcal{M}_{fog}}{\mathcal{M}}, \quad \mathcal{D}_c = \frac{\mathcal{M}_{cloud}}{\mathcal{M}} \quad (77)$$

Suppose that the demand agent i has visited \mathcal{J}_i resource agents with $\mathcal{J}_i - 1$ paths for movement. We can imply that the

Algorithm 2: Integrated Algorithm.

Input: Hormone values and incoming pods
Output: Path to a suitable resource agent

- 1 Initialization;
- 2 **for** $t \leftarrow 1$ **to** T_{final} **do**
- 3 **while** $\|\bar{\mathcal{C}}\| > \bar{\epsilon}$ **do**
- 4 Apply the CBRA strategy in Algorithm 1;
- 5 **if** Pods enter the continuum **then**
- 6 Select an initial resource agent by (75);
- 7 Check resource availability;
- 8 **while** Available resource is insufficient **do**
- 9 Choose a neighbor agent by (76);
- 10 Move to the selected resource agent;
- 11 Recheck resource availability.
- 12 Update the hormone level based on (74);

communication cost (CC) is zero if $\mathcal{J}_i = 1$. Define the average CC as $\bar{\mathcal{C}}$. It can be written as

$$\bar{\mathcal{C}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{\mathcal{M}} \sum_{k=1}^{\mathcal{J}_i-1} \mathcal{C}_k}{\mathcal{M}} \quad (78)$$

where \mathcal{C}_k represents the CC on the k^{th} path, $k \in [1, \mathcal{J}_i - 1]$.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In this section, we first conduct a simulation to validate the theoretical results of the CBRA strategy. After that, we construct an edge-fog-cloud continuum with arriving pods via agent-based modeling. The integrated algorithm is implemented in the continuum to manage the workload. Three simulation case studies are designed to discuss and compare the performance of the system using the HBA workload scheduler with and without the CBRA strategy.

A. Verification of the CBRA Strategy

First, we deploy the simulation to validate the theoretical results of the CBRA strategy. Their interaction topology is defined as a ring. Five resource agents are utilized in this case on the edge layer. The initial resource pool r_i is selected as [16,

Fig. 3. Iteration of the CPU and memory values using the standard consensus protocol.

Fig. 4. Iteration of the CPU and memory values using the standard consensus protocol with the same disturbances.

Fig. 5. Iteration of the CPU and memory values using the consensus protocol with disturbance compensator.

32], [20, 16], [32, 24], [24, 20], and [28, 28] for agents 1 to 5, respectively. We set the boundary of the disturbances as 2. The time interval T is set as 0.01.

1) *Standard CBRA Strategy*: We choose the control gain κ equals to 0.1 according to Theorem 1. By implementing the standard CBRA strategy to each agent with different disturbances, the iteration of the CPU and memory values is displayed in Fig. 3(a) and (b). It can be observed that both the CPU and memory values can converge closely to the consensus within a bounded consensus error. This verifies the results in Theorem 1.

In the next stage, we introduce the same disturbance to each agent. By applying the CBRA strategy, the iteration of the CPU and memory values is shown in Fig. 4(a) and (b). The results indicate that both the CPU and memory values converge to the consensus, which validates the theoretical results in Corollary 1.

2) *CBRA With Disturbance Compensator*: In this case, we will explore the performance of the CBRA strategy with a disturbance compensator. We select the control gains as $\kappa = 0.1$ and $D = 5$ on the basis of Theorems 2 and 3. The threshold ε in (55) is set as 0.01. Iteration of the CPU and memory values is demonstrated in Fig. 5 using the CBRA strategy with a disturbance compensator. It is evident that both the CPU

Fig. 6. Example of the generated edge-fog-cloud continuum.

and memory values can also converge to the consensus. This validates the theoretical results in Theorem 3.

To sum up, it can be obtained that the consensus error can be guaranteed in a bound set using the standard CBRA strategy. Specifically, the consensus error will converge to zero if the introduced disturbances are the same for each agent. Furthermore, the disturbance compensator designed in CBRA plays a key role in surpassing the affect of disturbances during the consensus process. That is to say, the CBRA strategy can be applied to assign the resource pool more uniformly.

B. Simulation Case Studies for Integrated Algorithm

The performance of the integrated algorithm is discussed in this section. The COSMOS (Continuum Optimization for Swarm-based Multi-tier Orchestration System) proposed in [7] is implemented as the simulation framework for the integrated algorithm. Then, we compare the performance of the integrated algorithm with the HBA workload scheduler only with different frequencies of arriving pods μ , probability of the connection in the edge network (PCE), and the variance of the initial resource distribution (VIRD) on the edge resource agents.

1) *Setup of the Simulation Framework*: We adopt COSMOS built on the Mesa library [47] to describe the edge-fog-cloud continuum in the Python environment. This framework is available open-source on GitHub. There are 10, 5, and 2 resource agents in the edge, fog, and cloud layers, respectively. The COSMOS simulates network communications by modeling the edge-fog-cloud continuum as a weighted graph where edge weights represent communication costs [7]. The connection between each agent is generated by NetworkX [48] to guarantee that the edge layer and the continuum are connected based on the description in Section III. One example of the generated edge-fog-cloud continuum is shown in Fig. 6. We set the intra-communication costs as 1 and 2 on the edge and fog layers. The inter-communication costs are defined as 8 and 30 for the edge-to-fog and fog-to-cloud, respectively.

Remark 5: The COSMOS simulation framework is specially designed for agent-based, decentralized, and self-organizing scheduling in the edge-fog-cloud continuum [7]. Compared with other widely used frameworks, such as iFogSim [49], which mainly focus on centralized fog-cloud placement, the COSMOS framework natively supports decentralized swarm-driven behavior and multi-tier interaction. These features motivate us

TABLE I
P-VALUES OF THE ALGORITHMS WITH DIFFERENT FREQUENCY OF ARRIVING PODS μ

Metrics	Algorithms	$\mu = 0.2$	$\mu = 0.4$	$\mu = 0.6$	$\mu = 0.8$	$\mu = 1$
DF	No-CBRA	1.21×10^{-15}	1.81×10^{-27}	5.99×10^{-29}	7.70×10^{-30}	2.69×10^{-28}
	CBRA-S	9.59×10^{-17}	1.74×10^{-26}	1.30×10^{-30}	1.32×10^{-31}	1.50×10^{-33}
	CBRA-C	2.77×10^{-17}	3.74×10^{-26}	2.15×10^{-28}	1.54×10^{-32}	4.22×10^{-36}
DC	No-CBRA	N/A	0.0042	2.02×10^{-9}	1.25×10^{-17}	1.79×10^{-20}
	CBRA-S	N/A	8.13×10^{-4}	3.17×10^{-13}	1.30×10^{-15}	2.87×10^{-23}
	CBRA-C	N/A	0.0058	3.46×10^{-11}	8.42×10^{-16}	1.76×10^{-20}
CC	No-CBRA	1.07×10^{-19}	7.53×10^{-16}	4.11×10^{-16}	1.00×10^{-21}	1.62×10^{-23}
	CBRA-S	1.51×10^{-17}	2.76×10^{-23}	1.02×10^{-21}	6.56×10^{-23}	2.16×10^{-28}
	CBRA-C	7.82×10^{-19}	6.99×10^{-23}	3.72×10^{-21}	1.90×10^{-22}	7.38×10^{-27}

to choose the COSMOS as the simulation framework in this paper.

Suppose that the capability of the resource agents in the fog layer is 64 or 128 units for CPU and memory. The capability of the cloud server is unlimited. The demand agents, pods, are classified into small, medium, and large pods according to their requirements. In this work, we define the upper bounds of the small, medium, and large pods as 2, 8, and 16, respectively, for both CPU and memory units. The probabilities of the small, medium, and large pods arriving in the continuum are set as 0.4, 0.4, and 0.2, respectively. For the parameters in the HBA scheduling, we choose $k_g = 0.6$, $k_d = 0.1$, and $k_p = 0.2$. The simulation iteration steps are selected as 1500.

Three candidates are selected to discuss the performance of the workload management. They are HBA scheduling without CBRA (no CBRA), an integrated algorithm for HBA scheduling with standard CBRA (CBRA-S), and an integrated algorithm for HBA scheduling with CBRA that includes a disturbance compensator (CBRA-C). We set $d^* = 0.1$ and $T = 0.01$ in the resource update system. $a_{ij} = 1$ if $(v_i, v_j) \in \mathcal{E}_e$, $i \neq j$, otherwise $a_{ij} = 0$. The control gains are chosen as $\kappa = 0.2$ and $D = 0.4$ based on the conditions in Theorem 1 and Theorem 3. After that, we explore the performance of the workload management based on three KPIs (DF, DC, and CC) defined in Section IV-C (77), (78) using the three candidates with different μ , PCE, and VIRID.

2) *Discussion With Different μ* : In this case, we first focus on fixing the frequency of the arriving pods as $\mu = 0.9$. The initial resource distribution of CPU and memory on edge resource agents follows a normal distribution with a mean of 24 and a variance of 5, which is shown in Fig. 7. We run the simulation 30 times for HBA scheduling with CBRA-C, CBRA-S, and no CBRA. The dependency of fog and cloud (DF/DC) and communication costs (CC) are presented in Fig. 8(a), (b), and (c) at each iteration step. The green, blue, and red zones cover all the results of the 30 times simulation using HBA without CBRA, with CBRA-S, and with CBRA-C, respectively. The mean value of each case is denoted by green, blue, and red solid lines. It can be observed that the dependency on fog/cloud (DF/DC) and communication costs (CC) can be reduced by introducing the CBRA into workload management. Moreover, the DF/DC and CC can be further decreased if we apply the modified CBRA with a disturbance compensator (CBRA-C).

Fig. 7. Initial resource distribution on edge resource agents with mean 24 and variance 5.

We then explore the performance with different frequencies of arriving pods, $\mu \in \{0.2, 0.4, 0.6, 0.8, 1\}$. After running 30 times of simulations for each μ using the three candidate algorithms. The box plot of DF/DC and CC is demonstrated in Fig. 9. Table I demonstrates the p-values of the three candidate algorithms with different μ for the statistical significance discussion. All the p-values satisfy the significance criterion ($p < 0.05$) and most of them are extremely small. The p-values are not applicable for DC with $\mu = 0.2$ since all observed values are zero for three algorithms, resulting in zero invariance. This is because the pods can be served on the edge and fog layer for the low frequency of the arriving demands. Hence, the obtained simulation results are statistically significant for all the algorithms with different μ . We can also obtain that the workload scheduler using HBA with CBRA outperforms HBA without CBRA with lower DF/DC and CC for different frequencies of pods.

3) *Discussion With Different PCE*: Here, we concentrate on discussing the performance of the workload management using three candidate algorithms with different probabilities of the connection in the edge network (PCE). We keep the frequency of the arriving pods as $\mu = 0.9$ and the distribution of the resource pool on edge resource agents shown in Section V-B2. The PCE is selected from $\{0.2, 0.8\}$. They represent sparse and dense network connections among edge resource agents. Two examples of the network generation in edge resource agents with different PCE are displayed in Fig. 10. We conduct 30 simulation runs for different PCE with three candidate algorithms. The DF/DC and CC are illustrated in Fig. 11, Fig. 12, and Fig. 13, respectively. Table II illustrates the p-values of the three candidate algorithms with different PCE at the last iteration step (1500)

Fig. 8. Dependency on fog (a), cloud (b), and communication costs (c) with frequency $\mu = 0.9$ using HBA with and without CBRA at each iteration step.

Fig. 9. Box plot of dependency on fog (a), cloud (b), and communication costs (c) with different frequencies μ using HBA with and without CBRA.

Fig. 10. Examples of the generated edge resource agent network with PCE selected as (a) 0.2 and (b) 0.8.

Fig. 12. Dependency on cloud using HBA with and without CBRA with PCE set as (a) 0.2 and (b) 0.8.

Fig. 11. Dependency on fog using HBA with and without CBRA with PCE set as (a) 0.2 and (b) 0.8.

Fig. 13. Communication costs using HBA with and without CBRA with PCE set as (a) 0.2 and (b) 0.8.

for the statistical significance discussion. It can be observed that all the p-values are extremely small ($p < 10^{-15}$). Hence, the obtained simulation results are statistically significant for all the algorithms with different PCE. It is evident that integrating the CBRA with the HBA workload scheduler contributes to lowering the DF/DC and CC for different PCE. The DF/DC and

CC can also be reduced additionally when applying the HBA scheduling with CBRA-C.

4) *Discussion With Different VIRD*: We now examine the performance of the workload management using three candidate algorithms with different variances of initial resource distribution (VIRD) on edge resource agents. The frequency of arriving

TABLE II
P-VALUES OF THE ALGORITHMS WITH DIFFERENT PCE

Metrics	Algorithms	0.2	0.8
DF	No-CBRA	2.24×10^{-31}	1.04×10^{-36}
	CBRA-S	1.37×10^{-35}	2.48×10^{-37}
	CBRA-C	3.54×10^{-32}	1.35×10^{-33}
DC	No-CBRA	6.05×10^{-17}	6.57×10^{-17}
	CBRA-S	7.93×10^{-18}	2.17×10^{-19}
	CBRA-C	4.85×10^{-16}	1.32×10^{-19}
CC	No-CBRA	1.44×10^{-22}	1.18×10^{-23}
	CBRA-S	6.12×10^{-22}	8.40×10^{-23}
	CBRA-C	1.18×10^{-20}	1.10×10^{-28}

Fig. 14. Initial resource distribution on edge resource agents with mean 24 and variance 2 (blue) and 8 (green).

Fig. 15. Dependency on fog using HBA with and without CBRA for VIRD set as (a) 2 and (b) 8.

Fig. 16. Dependency on cloud using HBA with and without CBRA for VIRD set as (a) 2 and (b) 8.

Pods is set as $\mu = 0.9$. We fix the mean value of the initial resource distribution in the edge resource agents to 24 for both CPU and memory. The VIRD is chosen from $\{2, 8\}$, which is illustrated in Fig. 14. They reflect the degree of balance in the initial resource distribution. We perform 30 simulations using three candidate algorithms for each VIRD. As shown in Fig. 15, Fig. 16, and Fig. 17, the DF/DC and CC are decreased if we combine the HBA workload scheduler with CBRA. Further

Fig. 17. Communication costs using HBA with and without CBRA for VIRD set as (a) 2 and (b) 8.

TABLE III
P-VALUES OF THE ALGORITHMS WITH DIFFERENT VIRD

Metrics	Algorithms	2	8
DF	No-CBRA	1.31×10^{-34}	1.02×10^{-32}
	CBRA-S	3.42×10^{-34}	1.08×10^{-34}
	CBRA-C	3.77×10^{-34}	9.09×10^{-29}
DC	No-CBRA	9.33×10^{-17}	1.07×10^{-20}
	CBRA-S	1.86×10^{-18}	3.09×10^{-18}
	CBRA-C	6.11×10^{-17}	2.42×10^{-16}
CC	No-CBRA	2.70×10^{-23}	1.21×10^{-26}
	CBRA-S	2.30×10^{-24}	7.38×10^{-24}
	CBRA-C	4.17×10^{-25}	6.83×10^{-22}

Fig. 18. Communication costs with different VIRD using HBA scheduling with (a) CBRA-C and (b) no CBRA.

reductions are also achieved when employing HBA scheduling with CBRA-C. Table III shows the p-values of the three candidate algorithms with different VIRD at the iteration step 1500 for the statistical significance discussion. It can be obtained that all the p-values are extremely small ($p < 10^{-15}$). Hence, the obtained simulation results are statistically significant for all the algorithms with different VIRD.

From Fig. 17(a) and (b), it is noticeable that the gap between communication costs (CC) using HBA with and without CBRA becomes larger if the VIRD increases from 2 to 8. To validate the adaptability of the workload management with the CBRA strategy, we further explore the communication costs with various VIRD from $\{1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10\}$. As demonstrated in Fig. 18(a) and (b), the CC remains stable using the HBA scheduling with CBRA-C, while it exhibits an increasing trend using HBA scheduling without CBRA. Therefore, the CC using HBA without CBRA is more sensitive to the increase of VIRD. That is to say, integrating CBRA-C into the HBA scheduling can improve the adaptability of the workload management with respect to the initial resource distribution of the edge resource agents.

Fig. 19. Communication costs under the proposed integrated algorithm (IA) and two baseline algorithms as: introducing a prox-based term presented in [50] (blue) and using ACO workload scheduler proposed in [19] (green).

To sum up, it can be concluded from all the results that the performance of the workload management can be optimized by integrating the CBRA strategy into the HBA workload scheduler with lower DF/DC and CC. These metrics can be further reduced when implementing the modified CBRA protocol (CBRA-C). On the other hand, the integrated algorithm also shows more adaptivity than the HBA scheduling without CBRA in terms of the initial resource distribution of the edge resource agents.

C. Comparison With Previous Work

In this section, we compare the performance of the proposed integrated algorithm (IA) with previous state-of-art approaches. For the proposed IA, we adopt the CBRA-C strategy with HBA scheduling for workload management. For the baseline algorithm, the first is inspired by the FedProx presented in [50]. We introduce the proximal term $\mu_P(r_i - \bar{r})$ in the standard CBRA strategy with the HBA scheduling. This prox-based algorithm is not fully decentralized since the global variable \bar{r} representing the average state is introduced for the resource update process. The robustness against unknown disturbances cannot be guaranteed by the prox-based algorithm, even though a proximal term is included. Another baseline algorithm is provided by the ACO workload scheduler in [19] without the CBRA strategy. The bound of the disturbance is set as $d^* = 0.2$ for the comparison. We choose the parameters as $D = 0.8$ for the proposed IA and $\mu_P = -0.1$ for the prox-based algorithm. For the ACO algorithm, we adopt the same parameter settings as in [19]. The number of simulation iterations is set to 1500, and each algorithm is executed 30 times.

The communication costs of the three algorithms are displayed in Fig. 19. The red, blue, and green zones cover all the results of the proposed IA, prox-based algorithm, and ACO algorithm. The mean values are denoted by the red, blue, and green lines. It can be observed that the CC value for the proposed IA is lower than that of the two baseline algorithms. The p-values shown in Table IV also reveal that the simulation results are statistically significant for all the algorithms. That is to say, the proposed IA outperforms the baseline algorithms for the lower communication costs.

TABLE IV
P-VALUES OF THE THREE ALGORITHMS

Algorithms	p-values
Proposed-IA	6.93×10^{-24}
Prox-based	1.80×10^{-19}
ACO	1.87×10^{-24}

D. Implementation in Mobility Use Case

In this section, we implement the proposed IA for workload management in the mobility use case. The main objective of the use case focuses on the intersection safety in connected and cooperative automated mobility for the MYRTUS project [51]. This scenario involves multiple heterogeneous actors, including vehicles, roadside infrastructure, and backend services. They should cooperate under dynamic and safety-critical traffic conditions. In this application, the system should deal with the workloads of varying computational complexity and urgency triggered by continuously changing traffic conditions, fluctuating resource availability, and diverse timing constraints. According to the traffic situation, computational tasks can range from simple to highly complex. To ensure reliable execution while balancing computational loads across the system, tasks may be dynamically offloaded from edge devices to fog layer or cloud servers. Hence, this use case can be modeled as a workload orchestration problem across an edge–fog–cloud continuum from a system-level perspective.

We first conduct the scalability analysis of the proposed IA for the mobility use case with different numbers of resource agents in the continuum. Suppose there are five, one, and three resource agents on edge, fog, and cloud layers for the basic network, with the frequency of the arriving demand agents as $\mu = 0.8$. We set the initial resource distribution of CPU and memory on edge resource agents to follow a normal distribution with a mean of 41 and 96, and a variance of 8 and 10 in this use case. Define SF as the scaling factor based on the basic network ($Q_e = 5, Q_f = 1, Q_c = 3$). When the number of resource agents is scaled up, the corresponding arriving demand agents will also be scaled up accordingly. We explore the performance of the proposed IA with different $SF \in \{1, 2, 5, 10, 20\}$. Then, the number of the edge nodes is selected from $Q_e \in \{5, 10, 25, 50, 100\}$. The communication cost (CC) of the proposed IA with different numbers of edge nodes is illustrated in Fig. 20. We can observe that the increase of the CC is not as much as the increase of the size of the continuum (about 25% for $SF = 20$ from $Q_e = 5$ scale up to $Q_e = 100$). That is to say, the proposed IA exhibits the scalability for the implementation in the mobility use case.

In the next stage, we compare the performance of the proposed IA with three baseline algorithms for the mobility use case with $Q_e = 100$ with $SF = 20$. The baseline algorithms are HBA scheduling without CBRA (HBA only), the ACO algorithm proposed in [19], and the random workload scheduler algorithm. Under the random workload scheduler algorithm, the demands agents randomly choose a resource agent from the neighbors if the available resources are not enough, as presented [19]. The communication costs of the algorithms are shown in Fig. 21.

Fig. 20. Communication costs of the proposed IA with different numbers of edge nodes for the mobility use case.

Fig. 21. Communication costs of the proposed IA with three baseline algorithms for large-scale continuum $Q_e = 100$.

TABLE V
P-VALUES OF THE ALGORITHMS

Algorithms	p-values
Proposed-IA	5.72×10^{-22}
HBA only	5.46×10^{-22}
ACO	2.70×10^{-22}
Random	3.34×10^{-18}

The results are covered by red, blue, green, and yellow zones for each algorithm. The red, blue, green, and yellow solid lines stand for the mean values. The p-values demonstrated in Table V also indicate that the results are statistically significant for all the algorithms. Hence, we can obtain that the proposed IA still performs better than the baseline algorithms for the lower communication costs in the large-scale mobility use case.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, the decentralized workload management approach is discussed in the edge–fog–cloud continuum. We apply the consensus technique in resource allocation to assign the resource pool uniformly for the edge layer. A standard CBRA is first presented for the resource update in the presence of disturbances. We provide the robustness analysis and introduce a compensator to tackle the disturbances during the update. This proposed CBRA strategy is integrated with a workload scheduler based on the hormone algorithm. After that, we establish a simulation framework to validate the integrated algorithm that

includes HBA scheduling with the CBRA strategy. The simulation results reveal that workload management can be optimized using HBA scheduling with the CBRA strategy. The integrated algorithm is also more adaptive in terms of the initial resource distribution. The performance of the integrated algorithm is also explored in the mobility use case. In the future, we will further improve the resource allocation algorithm via resilient and learning-based methods to tackle the communication issue and apply the integrated algorithm of edge-fog-cloud continuum to real-world platforms.

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